

ENCOURAGEMENT OF SOCIAL INITIATIVES IN THE MAHALLA

M. Yunusova

associate professor of AndSU

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Abstract: The thesis deals with the issues of encouraging civil initiatives in the activities of self-governing bodies. The prospects of using the models developed by the world's leading experts are revealed.

Key words: neighborhood, initiative, civil society, social activity

At the current stage of civil society development in Uzbekistan, a number of problems of citizen mobilization are clearly visible in neighborhood activities.

Firstly, due to the fact that salaries and financing are from the district and city budgets, most of the chairpersons are busy collecting taxes, collecting fees, and helping to hold various events, which are not part of their authority. Acceptance of citizens, hearing and solving their problems has become secondary. Surveys and observations show that self-governance mobilization activities are almost non-existent.

Secondly, because the neighborhood is not part of the state authorities, there is no legal basis for its relations with other district or city organizations. In some districts and cities, the activities of neighborhood chairmen are effective, and in others, they are not related to the neighborhood.

Thirdly, in the current conditions, there is no effective methodology for bringing the problems of citizens to the neighborhood in an organized manner. Five thousand citizens in the neighborhood may have five thousand problems. But some of them need to be solved immediately, but the solutions for finding an answer to the question have not been developed.

These problems have a systemic nature and require the development and popularization of a certain new system of traditions and values.

In this regard, the experience of the Rural Infrastructure Development Project implemented in Uzbekistan by the International Development Association of the World Bank [1] can be used.

American scientist Bridget Bodeyo[2], who was involved in the project as a trainer, conducted a series of trainings on the role of mobilization and its organization in solving neighborhood problems.

It is known that the decision-making process in the neighborhoods remains uncertain. Therefore, the public does not have enough information about the decisions made in the neighborhoods. This leads to the fact that the decisions made in the neighborhood are not only implemented, but also not at the level of awareness. In order to solve such problems, a new approach to the decision-

making process in the neighborhood is needed, and one can refer to the experience of Brigitte Bode[3].

It should be noted that Brigit Bode's Rural Development Plan is aimed at targeting the funds allocated by the citizens from the World Bank in a certain neighborhood - directing them to the most urgent problem and establishing public control over its implementation. The materials provided by the Andijan regional branch of the National Movement of Upliftment, the facilitators who participated in this project - Azizbek Egamberdiev and Bekhzod Yusupov, as well as video lectures available in open sources were studied.

Based on the studies, a mechanism of regular decision-making process was developed in the community.

It is known that according to Article 9 of the current Law on "Citizens' Self-Governing Bodies", "Citizens' Assembly represents the interests of the population and makes decisions on its behalf that are valid within the relevant territory."

People who have reached the age of eighteen and are permanently living in the relevant area will participate in the citizens' meeting. This norm remains one of the norms that rarely works in practice. For example, the community assembly wants to promote a project in an open budget competition. Is it the priority to repair a school in the neighborhood, build a water facility or pave a road? Each of these problems can be prepared at length on the basis of necessity. At the same time, there is no mechanism of how to come to a certain decision when solving various issues related to the life of the neighborhood. In this situation, it is necessary to improve the current situation in the community meeting and create conditions for citizens to freely express their thoughts and opinions, while respecting the interests of others. One side of the issue is that there is no example of a meeting with the participation of every resident over the age of 18 and a certain decision was made. This norm was written in the spirit of direct democracy, similar to the time of ancient Athens, and did not take into account the fact that the population of many classes lived in the neighborhood (in Athens, women and slaves did not participate in decision-making, and the level of the electorate was close to each other).

Under the system we propose, the neighborhood chairman's advisers are central to decision-making.

During the election process, only the head of the neighborhood citizens vote for the candidate of the head of the neighborhood, and the mandate of the neighborhood councilors is determined after the election in agreement with the

precinct election commission and the head of the neighborhood. It is advisable to take into account the number of streets, the distance between them and the peculiarities of other neighborhoods. In our opinion, it is better for them to select two women and one man for each of up to 10 streets in the neighborhood. If the number of streets is small, the number of consultants may be reduced accordingly. However, the number of advisers in the neighborhood should be at least 8 and at most 20.

After the election for the position of neighborhood chairman, councilors from the designated streets should be recommended by the residents. In this case, the precinct election commission will have to ensure that advisers belonging to different strata of the population, with an equal number of men and women, are recommended in agreement with the population.

After the composition of the consultants is formed, it will be necessary to participate in seminars and trainings on issues such as analysis of social and material resources of the neighborhood, solving problems in the field of education, analysis of the state of health and studying the causes of poverty according to the model created by Brigitte Bode.

As soon as the chairman and advisers of the neighborhood begin their work, it will be possible to create an opportunity for the activists of the neighborhood to look at their activities in a critical spirit once again by organizing these seminars with the strength of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions in each region.

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The project will be implemented from 2020 to 2024 in five regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Jizzakh, Syrdarya, Ferghana, Namangan, and Andijan, covering 21 districts and more than 300 villages in these regions. The Project's development objectives are to: (i) improve the quality of basic infrastructure, and (ii) strengthen participatory local governance processes in selected villages.

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